

Call for Papers

International Journal of Ad hoc, sensor & Ubiquitous Computing (IJASUC) is a bi monthly open access peer-reviewed journal provides excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Ad Hoc & Ubiquitous computing. Current information age is witnessing a dramatic use of digital and electronic devices in the workplace and beyond. Ubiquitous Computing presents a rather arduous requirement of robustness, reliability and availability to the end user. Ad hoc, Sensor & Ubiquitous computing has received a significant and sustained research interest in terms of designing and deploying large scale and high performance computational applications in real life.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following.

- Ad Hoc Networks of Autonomous Intelligent Systems
- Addressing and Location Management
- Architectures, Protocols and Algorithms
- Data Management Issues
- Distributed Technology
- Mobile Ad Hoc Learning
- Mobile and Wireless Ad Hoc Networks
- Mobile Agents for Ad Hoc Networking
- Network Design and Planning
- Novel Architectures for Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks
- Performance Analysis and Simulation of Protocols
- Power-Aware and Energy-Efficient Designs
- Quality of Service
- Resource Allocation
- Security and Privacy
- Self-Configuring and Self-Healing Schemes
- Services and Applications
- Wireless & Mobile Network Security
- Wireless Sensor Networks

Sensor Networks

- Architectures, Protocols and Algorithms
- Data allocation and Information
- Deployments and Implementations
- Embedded, Network-Oriented Operating Systems
- Energy Optimization
- Hardware Aspects of Sensor Design
- Location Management and Placement
- MAC Protocols for Wireless Sensor Networks
- Middleware and Software Tools
- Modeling and Performance Evaluation

- Radio Issues with Other Wireless/Mobile Systems
- Resource Allocation, Services, QoS and Fault Tolerance
- Scalability of Wireless Sensor Networks
- Security and Dependability Issues
- Sensor Circuits and Devices
- Software, Applications and Programming
- Under Water Sensors and Systems
- Visualization of Sensor Data

Ubiquitous Computing

- Architectural Structure, Design Decisions and Philosophies
- Autonomic Management of Ubiquitous Systems
- Context and Location Awareness, Context Based and Implicit Computing
- Distributed Computing
- Ubicomp Human-Computer Interaction for Devices
- Intelligent Devices and Environments
- Internet Computing and Applications
- Interoperability and Large Scale Deployment
- Middleware Services and Agent Technologies
- Personalized & Special Field Applications
- Security Issues and Applications
- Service Discovery Mechanisms and Protocols
- Software Infrastructures
- System Support Infrastructures and Services
- Ubiquitous Systems and Trust
- User Interfaces and Interaction Models
- Virtualization Over Networks of Devices
- Wearable Computers and Technologies
- Wireless Networking and Mobile, Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing
- Wireless/Mobile Service Management and Delivery
- Mobile Computing
- Network Protocols & Wireless Communication
- Work Models

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail : ijasucjournal@aircse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Date

- **Submission Deadline : December 12, 2020**
- Notification : January 12, 2021
- Final Manuscript Due : January 20, 2021
- PublicationDate : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

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